

Correlation of Stress and Coping Strategies with Achievement Motivation of University Students

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: Januari 17, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: April 21, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Correlation, Stress, Coping Strategies, Achievement Motivation, University Students</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4708077</p>	<p><i>The impact of stress and coping strategies on achievement motivation of university students was examined in this study. The current study was descriptive in nature and cross-sectional survey method was applied for the collection of data. Population of this study comprised of public sector universities of Islamabad. To select representative sample from the population, disproportionate stratified random sampling technique was used. The sample consisted of 756 students from two universities of Islamabad. In this study, three standardized instruments were used to measure stress developed by Barreca & Hepler (2000), coping strategies developed by David & Alexandra (1995) and achievement motivation developed by Mclnerney (2003). Data were analysed by applying mean, standard deviation, t-test and correlation. Research findings reveals that there is significant difference in responses between male and female university students regarding coping strategies and achievement motivation, this study also reveals that there is significant relationship between student's stress and achievement motivation and it also reveals that coping strategies have positive correlation with achievement motivation. It is recommended that higher authorities of educational organizations may organize orientation seminars, regular stress management programs, and guidance and counseling services to meet the need of students and to achieve their academic targets effectively.</i></p>

Introduction

Stress is an essential part of our lives. It increases taste, challenges and chances to our lives, allowing us to achieve our goals, make the experience more exciting, and the event is full of challenges. But, the benefits of stress do not exceed a definite level of stress (Ivanecovich & Matteson, 1980), then once this level is exceeded, stress can adversely affect physical and mental health (Bartlett, 1998), which can lead to nervousness, anxiety, touchiness, fatigue, metabolic imbalance and decreased immunity in the body. Recently, surprising trends have been found in the observed stress of the pupils (Sax, 1997).

After entering the university, there will be some changes in the youth. The tasks that occur in this new phase of his life, such as the need for university campuses, hard daily life and variation to the environment can create stress. After a stressful event, everyone has their own limits and ways to balance. The more flexible it is, the more schemes it uses, the longer the individual can resist the stress-causing factors, and when the body does not find a solution to the stress, it will be affected, causing physical symptoms such as flu, gastrointestinal discomfort, headache, high blood pressure and psychological anxiety, pessimism, fatigue, etc. (Belintani, 2016). Coping is a complex psychological process through which one can handle stress, solve problems and make decisions. This is the patient's emotional, cognitive and behavioral response to the disease. The response process involves at least two stages: facing and managing different aspects of the disease or disability (Šprah & Šoštarič, 2004). Because each child is a unique person, emotional, cognitive, and behavioral responses can vary greatly and occasionally become unpredictable. According to Folkman & Lazarus's coping strategies can be divided into two general types; problem-centric, focus on emotional response. A problem-centric response is designed to solve problems or do something that changes the source of stress. Emotion-centered responses are designed to reduce or manage emotional distress associated with the situation. While most stress factors trigger two types of responses, when people think that constructive things can be done, problem-centric responses tend to dominate, and when people think that stressors are things that must be tolerated, Emotion-centered responses tend to dominate (Folkman & Lazarus 1980).

A psychological basis for achievement of student is the encouragement and ambition of learners in the classroom climate. Motivation goal orientation has been shown to influence student learning strategies in the classroom, metacognitive strategies employed by students, participation and academic achievement, and students' goals and aspirations for the future. Goal orientation is often defined as a comprehensive model of

motivational beliefs that represent the proximity of activities related to achievement, the different ways of participation and response (Ames, 1992). According to the achievement goal theory (Ames, 1992) and McInerney, Yeung, and McInerney (2001) propose a stratified, having many dimensional motivational model of goal orientation that includes a series of considered to be related to Western and non-targets related goals. - Western culture. This outlines the relationship between first-order eight definite goals those are tasks, adoration, competition, effort, community power, tokens, community concerns and attribution on a hierarchical basis may be divided into three higher order aspects those are social, mastery and performance.

It has been shown that mastery, performance and social orientation can influence achievement in many different ways. Many researches concentrated on mastery and performance orientation, equally referred to as "knowledge and self-targeting." Goal-oriented students are focused on knowledge, belief and mastering tasks. (Pintrich, Marx and Boyle, 1993). These learners understands that hard work will lead to favorable outcomes and build their achievements on self-referential standard and performance-oriented students understands that their sense of self-worth and their capability to do better than others, beyond values and gain public acceptance. (Ames, 1992)

Literature Review

Stress

When your body act in answer to something it means that this is the action of stress. The human's body releasing chemical into blood when they feel stress about what is going on around them. Such chemicals give strength and energy to people and stress is good thing when it is caused by physical danger but it can also be a bad thing if their stress is a reaction to emotions and there is no such extra way of energy and strength.

To regard the stress of college students as a purely academic origin is to simplify its nature and understate its consequences. Research from around the world on the pressures of higher education students identifies some of the stressors that influence higher education students, finance or students related to time management (Goodman, 1993). Research-related stress itself is a major source of emotional distress (Stewart-Brown et al., 2000).

Problems outside the academic environment can also affect a student's life stress and require them to cope with their abilities. In this case, a major source of stress may be working family role conflicts (Hammer and Thompson 2003). The relationship between new friends and partners, especially intimacy, puts pressure on students.

Theories

Theories of stress focus on specific relations among external needs considers as stressors and physical processes considers as stress can be divided into two sorts: "systemic stress" methods based on physiology and psychology (Selye 1976) and "psychological methods" pressures. It was developed in the field of cognitive psychology (Lazarus 1966, 1991, Lazarus and Folkman 1984, McGrath 1982).

Selye's Theory

The status of the concept of stress in science and mass media is mainly due to the work of endocrinologist named Hans Selye. He seen that various stimulating events (eg, heat, cold, poison) are strongly applied and long enough to produce a common effect, which means that they are not specific for any stimulus event in a series of animal studies. (In addition to these non-specific variations in the body, every motivation of way produces its definite effects, like, vasodilation. Selye said that these non-specific variations represent a stereotype, a specific reaction of general stress pattern. Selye (1976) describes stress as a state revealed by a disorder consisting of all non-specifically stimulated variations in the biotic method.

The Lazarus Theory

The twofold ideas are at the heart of any theory of psychological stress: assessment, the assessment of the importance of an individual's well-being, and the individual's efforts to manage specific needs in thinking and acting (Lazarus, 1993). In the newest form, stress is considered a relationship concept that stress is not described as a specific kind of external stimulus, nor is it a specific pattern of physiological and behavioral responses (Lazarus 1991). Stress is seen as the connection between the individual and his or her climate ("transactions"). Stress refers to the connection between people and the environment. It is important to his or her well-being and requires taxation or surrender of obtainable coping possessions (Lazarus & Folkman 1986). The portrayal points to two procedures as main moderators in human-environmental transactions: cognitive assessment and response. Holmes and Rahe (1967) pointed out that any life change that requires a lot of adjustments can be considered stressful. Many students try to confuse their busy lives. They are under pressure from school and work; they also try to spend time with family and friends. For some students, stress is almost a way of life. However, letting stress be a way for students to live in college is really dangerous, because a certain degree of stress can lead to terrible consequences, completely change students' lives and lead to failure.

Coping Strategies

The conception of coping is founded on three theoretic factors: physiology, cognition, and learning. Physiologically, system of body has its own way to deal with painful events. Individual threats or challenges in the environment may lead to a cascade emotional arousal and neuroendocrine events involving the secretion of catechol amines and corticosteroids (Frankenhaeuser, 1986). Studies in the United Kingdom have considered

the coping strategies of medical students to cope with the pressure of undergraduate education, and generally use alcohol as a coping strategy (Guthrie et al., 1995; Campbell et al., 1998), but there are some reports describing tobacco use and drugs (Miller and Surtees, 1991; Ashton and Kamali, 1995). A study in Pakistan reported that sports, music, and gathering with friends are common coping strategies (Shaikh et al., 2004). The ability to complete tasks in a peaceful and thoughtful manner, and people who encounter problems or difficulties are one way to deal with them. Students are often under pressure from various problems, which makes them under pressure in a single or other way (Strong et al., 2008).

Mostly, coping refers to trying to allow and minimize the outcomes of stress, whether it is the involvement of stress itself or the source of stress. Coping theory can be categorized according to direction or focus (trait-oriented or country-oriented) and methods (macro or micro-analysis).

Classification of Coping Theories

Coping theories is distributed into two distinctive factors:

1. Trait-Oriented Theories versus State-Oriented Theories
2. Micro analytic Approach versus Macro analytic Approach

The trait-oriented theory emphasizes on the early identification of a person's supplies and the coping-related tendencies. Though, the country-oriented theory emphasizes the individual's actual response and the results of his application of coping methods. Although microscopic analysis methods have studied various specific and specific coping strategies, macroscopic analysis methods have focused on basic and abstract coping methods.

Achievement Motivation

Achievement motivation is considered to be one of the important aspects of human motivation system. For a long time, social psychology and personality researchers have paid attention to achievement motivation (McClelland, 1985). The term achievement motivation in psychology refers to Alfred Adler (Alfred Adler), who pointed out that achievement motivation is a compensatory motivation derived from childhood experiences (Wang, 1992). Murray also believes that the need for motivation is one of the important motivations of mankind. He was the first to accurately propose this concept as an important part of personal composition (Weiner, 1986). In the 1960s, many studies were proposed to ask about the scale, elements, and quality of the concept (Martin, 2007). McClelland (1985) defines it as ready, characterized by achieving comparative constancy of accomplishment and success, and this preparation is left in the body until some stimulus is stimulated under certain circumstances, and he believes that achievement Behavior returns hope of disappointment or accomplishment. In addition, Kinchella and Glucksberg said that achievement motivation includes hard work, the desire to face high standards and surpass others (Zanobini&Usui, 2002). Achievements can be divided into the following categories.

- Behavior style (cognition, emotion and tools)
- Type of confrontation (self confrontation and problem confrontation)
- Time perspective (before, after and after completing the task)

There is no doubt that achievement motivation is regarded as one of the most important themes in motivation psychology, because the need for achievement motivation is one of the criteria related to social progress (Butler, 1999). Rabideau (2007) defines achievement motivation as the realization of the necessity or superiority of achievement. But achievement motivation is constructed to allow us to obtain all the wishes in life, which means that our behavior is full of vitality.

Objectives

1. To comprehend the level of stress, coping strategies and achievement motivation among university students
2. To measure the correlation between dimensions of stress, coping strategies and achievement motivation among university students.
3. To investigate the effect of stress and achievement motivation on university students.
4. To investigate the ways of coping strategies that student's deal in their day to day lives and its influence on their achievement motivation.
5. To find out the significant difference among gender determining the stress, coping strategies and achievement motivation of university students.

Hypotheses

Ho1: University students have high level of stress.

Ho2: University students have high level of coping strategies.

Ho3: University students have high level of achievement motivation

Ho4: There is no correlation between the dimensions of stress and achievement motivation for university students.

Ho5: There is no correlation between the dimensions of ways of coping strategies and achievement motivation for university students.

Ho6: There is no impact of stress on achievement motivation of university students

Ho7: There is no impact of coping strategies on achievement motivation of university students.

Ho8: There is no significant difference among gender determining their stress.

Ho9: There is no significant difference among gender determining their coping strategies.

Ho10: There is no significant difference among gender determining their achievement motivation.

Conceptual Framework of the Research Study

A conceptual framework is the idea of the researcher that indicates a path of the research study. A conceptual framework of this research study is designed based on traditional model of stress and coping, hierarchical factor analysis and personal investment model. According to Lazarus and Folkman (1984), the interaction occurs among person and environment. Wherry (1984) identified eight primary factors of coping strategies in hierarchical factor analysis namely problem solving, cognitive restructuring, emotional expression, social support, problem avoidance, wishful thinking, self-criticism and social withdrawal. Achievement motivation is based on Personal Investment model developed by Maehr (1984). He describes that the person who has the skill to make selections in their lives be influenced by the meaning the choices have for him.

Methods and Procedures

The study was descriptive and quantitative in nature. Population of this study comprised of students of public sector universities of Islamabad. In order to select sample from the population, disproportionate stratified random sampling technique was used. The sample of 756 students (379 male and 377 female) were taken from two universities of Islamabad. The sample was taken according to L.R. Gay (2012). Three standardized questionnaires were used in this research those were Stress Indicator Questionnaire (SIQ) developed by Barreca & Hepler (2000) consisted of 4 dimensions and 32 number of items, Coping Strategies Inventory (CSI) developed by David L. Tobin (1995) consisted of 8 sub dimensions and 32 number of items and General Achievement Goal Orientation Scale (GAGOS) by McInerney (2003) consisted of 3 subscales and 18 number of items. Cronbach's Alpha statistical technique was used to measure the reliability of the questionnaires. The reliability of the instruments was .867, .724 and .812 respectively. Data were analyzed by using mean, standard deviation, t-test, correlation and regression.

Results

Table 1

Level of Stress

Dimensions	Mean	SD
University	17.8466	5.5136
Money	12.9735	3.6096
Relationship	18.9365	5.0256
Body, mind and feelings	19.2209	4.4507

Table 1 indicates the level of stress among university students. This table shows that dimension "Body, mind and feelings" have high mean score as compared to others dimensions of stress among university students.

Table 2

Level of Coping Strategies

Dimensions	Mean	SD
Problem Solving	11.6270	3.77668
Cognitive Restructuring	12.6045	3.19576
Express Emotions	11.1032	2.83870
Social Contact	12.6548	3.41421
Problem Avoidance	11.4603	3.13827
Wishful Thinking	11.8452	3.59044
Self-Criticism	11.9749	3.22583
Social Withdrawal	11.4696	5.61175

Table 2 shows the level of coping strategies between university students. This tables reveals that dimension “Cognitive Restructuring” and “Social Contact” have high mean score value as compared to other dimensions of coping strategies.

Table 3

Level of Achievement Motivation

Dimensions	Mean	SD
Mastery Goal	17.8426	5.28728
Performance Goal	29.5608	5.32646
Social Goal	16.9630	4.40364

Table 3 explain the level of achievement motivation among university students. This table indicates that mean score dimension “Performance Goal” is high as compared to other dimensions of achievement motivation.

Table 4

Correlation between dimensions of stress and achievement motivation

Dimensions	U	M	R	BMF	MG	PG	SG
U	1.00	-	-	-	-	-	-
M	.242**	1.00	-	-	-	-	-
R	.411**	.571**	1.00	-	-	-	-
BMF	.221**	.177**	.520**	1.00	-	-	-
MG	.112**	-.248**	-.106**	-.064	1.00	-	-
PG	.227**	-.200**	.022	.132**	.314**	1.00	-
SG	.244**	.307**	.260**	.045*	.219**	.535**	1.00

Keys: U: University, M: Money, R: Relationship, BMF: Body, mind and feelings, MG: Mastery Goal, PG: Performance Goal & SG: Social Goal

Table 4 indicates that there was positive and significant correlation was found between all the dimensions of stress and achievement motivation of university students i.e University ($r = .244$), money ($r = .307$), relationship ($r = .260$), body, mind and feelings ($r = .045$), mastery goal ($r = .219$) and performance goal ($r = .535$).

Table 5

Correlation between dimensions of coping strategies and achievement motivation

Dimension s	PS	CR	EE	S.Con	PA	WT	S.Crit	SW	MG	PG	SG
PS	1.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
CR	.745*	1.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
EE	.283*	.550*	1.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S.Con	.219*	.480*	.572*	1.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PA	.235*	.352*	.222*	.277*	1.00	-	-	-	-	-	-
WT	.291*	.390*	.561*	.390*	.627*	1.00	-	-	-	-	-
SCrit	.454*	.603*	.211*	.145*	.425*	.446*	1.00	-	-	-	-
SW	.248*	.215*	.174*	.236*	.347*	.253*	.301*	1.00	-	-	-
MG	.310*	.361*	.137*	.329*	.192*	.241*	.137*	.174*	1.00	-	-
PG	.171*	.265*	.223*	.469*	.296*	.270*	.127*	.074*	.314*	1.00	-
SG	.264*	.399*	.344*	.200*	.028	.108*	.195*	.059	.219*	.535*	1.00

Keys: PS: Problem Solving, CR: MG: Mastery Goal, PG: Performance Goal & SG: Social Goal

Table 5 indicates that there was positive and significant correlation among coping strategies and achievement motivation of university students' i.e Problem Solving ($r = .264$), Cognitive Restructuring ($r = .399$), Express Emotions ($r = .344$), Social Contact ($r = .200$), Problem Avoidance ($r = .028$), Wishful Thinking ($r = .108$), Self-Criticism ($r = .195$), Social Withdrawal ($r = .059$), Mastery Goal ($r = .219$) and Performance Goal ($r = .535$).

Table 6

Model Summary of Stress and Achievement Motivation

Model	R	R- Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.823 ^a	.678	.678	6.44080

a. Predictors: (constant), Stress

Table 6 shows that model summary of regression analysis of stress and achievement motivation of university students. Regarding this model summary correlation R is .832 and R-square is .678.

Table 7

ANOVA of Stress and Achievement Motivation

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	p
1	Regression	65866.665	1	65866.665	1587.766	.000 ^a
	Residual	31278.841	754	41.484		
	Total	97145.507	755			

a. Dependent Variable: achievement motivation

b. Predictors: (constant), Stress

ANOVA summary of stress and achievement motivation was showed in the table. It exposes that the regression equation is significant $F(1, 754) = 41.484$, $p = .000$. Hence, stress was a significant predictor to predict achievement motivation.

Table 8

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig
	B	Std. Error	Beta		

1 (Constant)	12.530	1.322		9.479	.000
Stress	1.754	.044	.823	39.847	.000

This table illustrates the coefficient summary of the model. It displays that the value of coefficient stress was 1.754 and, its t value is 39.847 which is significant at the .05 level as $p=.000$. It means there was a significant difference between stress and achievement motivation of university students.

Table 9

Model Summary of Coping Strategies and Achievement Motivation

Model	R	R- Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.741 ^a	.550	.549	7.61759

a. Predictor: (constant) coping strategies

Table 9 indicates the model summary of regression analysis of coping strategies and achievement motivation of university students. According to this model summary correlation R is .741 and R-square is .550.

Table 10

ANOVA of Coping Strategies and Achievement Motivation

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	53392.675	1	53392.675	920.125	.000 ^b
	Residual	43752.832	754	58.028		
	Total	97145.507	755			

a. Dependent Variable: achievement motivation

b. Predictors: (constant) Coping Strategies

ANOVA summary of coping strategies and achievement motivation was explained in this table. This table also reveals that the regression equation is significant $F(1, 754)= 58.028$, $p=.000$. Hence, coping strategies was a significant predictor to expect achievement motivation of university students.

Table 11

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	
1 (Constant)	31.973	1.103		28.980	.000
Coping Strategies	1.910	.063	.741	30.334	.000

This table illustrates the coefficient summary of the model. It displays that the value of coefficient coping strategies was 1.910 and, its t value is 30.334 which is significant at the .05 level as $p=.000$. It means there was a significant difference between coping strategies and achievement motivation of university students.

Table 12

Mean, Standard deviation and t- test for the variable stress

Gender	N	M	SD	df	t	p
Male	379	29.23	6.024			
Female	377	29.89	4.502			
	754	-1.70	.089			

Table 12 indicates that according to results mean average scores of university students. It portrays that stress level is approximately same in female as compared to male. ($M_{female} 29.89 \geq M_{male} 29.23$) whereas p value is .089; therefore, this difference is insignificant.

Table 13

Mean, Standard deviation and t- test for the variable Coping Strategies

Gender	N	M	SD	df	t	p
Male	379	16.17	4.663			
Female	377	17.73	3.985			
	754	-4.89	.000			

Table 13 implies that according to results mean average scores of university students regarding copying strategies those they use in their day to day life. It shows that coping stress level used by students is less than in

male as compared to female. (Mmale 16.17 < Mfemale 17.73) whereas p value is .000; therefore, this difference is significant.

Table 14

Mean, Standard deviation and t- test for the variable Achievement Motivation

Gender	N	M	SD	df	t	p
Male	379	63.42	12.487			
	754		-2.301		.022	
Female	377	65.31	9.990			

Table 14 reveals that according to results mean average scores of university students regarding achievement motivation. It displays that achievement motivation is higher than in female than male. (Mmale 63.42 < Mfemale 65.31) whereas p value is .022; therefore, this difference is significant.

Discussion

The research emphasis on objectives of the study which were to investigate the effect of stress and achievement motivation on university students, to investigate the ways of coping stress and its influence on their achievement motivation and to compare the effect of stress, coping stress and achievement motivation of male and female university students. The hypotheses were stated to test the objectives presented above.

According to the first hypothesis, a positive relationship was noted between stress and achievement motivation. In other words, students who have high level of stress had a higher score of achievement motivation or students whose level of stress decreased then their achievement motivation increased. The result located with the opposite findings of Dong (2014) who found a negative significant relationship with stress and achievement motivation. The results of the study showed that students with higher academic pressure had lower achievement motivation. But in another study Akif (2016) found that there was no significant relationship between academic stress and achievement motivation.

According to second hypothesis, the results revealed that there is strong and significant relationship between coping strategies and achievement motivation. In other words university students who can cope up their stress by using coping strategies efficiently had higher achievement motivation or the students who don't use coping strategies had not higher achievement. In the study of Acharya & Manjulata (2018) it was also found that there is a significant relationship between the athlete's achievement motivation and his/her coping proficiencies.

According to last hypothesis, the result of the study revealed that level of stress is higher as compared to the male. Another study from Matud (2004) showed that the women scored significantly higher than the men in habitual stress and slight daily stressors. The results of study also showed that male students use less coping strategies than females. Another studies resembled with finding of the study that male was more stressful due to poor coping strategies than female. (Shaikh et al., 2004; Pariat et al., 2014). The result of the study revealed that achievement motivation is higher than in female than male. Sampath & Maruthachalan (2000) found the same result that most of the university students with average achievement motivation are female respondents who belong to urban areas.

Conclusion

Following conclusions were drawn:

1. It is concluded that body, mind and feelings have high mean score in all dimensions of stress.
2. It is concluded that cognitive restructuring and social contact have high level of mean score in the dimensions of coping strategies of university students.
3. It is concluded that performance goal have high mean score in the dimensions of achievement motivation of university students.
4. It is concluded that there is positive and significant relationship between the dimensions of stress and achievement motivation.
5. It is concluded that there is positive and significant relationship between coping strategies and achievement motivation.
6. It is concluded that there is strong relationship between stress and achievement motivation.
7. It is concluded that there is strong relationship between coping strategies and achievement motivation.
8. It is concluded that female university students have higher level of stress as compared to male.
9. It is concluded that male students use less coping strategies than female.
10. It is concluded that achievement motivation is greater in female than male.

Recommendations

In the light of these findings, the researchers therefore recommended that:

- Students with dis-adaptive stress coping strategies must be trained and motivated to use effective coping strategies for stress management.
- Stress management program should be the integral part of the students' training.

- Higher authorities of educational organizations may organize orientation seminars, regular stress management programs, and guidance and counseling services to meet the need of students and to achieve their academic targets effectively.

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